

Monacha cartusiana (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) in South Bohemia

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The first record of non-indigenous expanding mollusc species *Monacha cartusiana* (O.F. Müller, 1774) is reported – the species was found on a dam of a coal-ash settling basin near České Budějovice.

Key words: *Monacha cartusiana*, Czech Republic, new finds, spreading

Introduction

Monacha cartusiana (O.F. Müller, 1774) (Gastropoda: Hygromiidae) is a west and south European species. In the Czech Republic, *M. cartusiana* was formerly relatively rare and scarce distributed, restricted to several isolated parts of country (LOŽEK 1956); recently, *M. cartusiana* have expanded (MÍKOVCOVÁ & JUŘIČKOVÁ 2008) and can occur in artificial habitats (JUŘIČKOVÁ & KUČERA 2007).

Locality and methods

The coal-ash settling basin is situated on the edge of the town of České Budějovice, between the parts of České Budějovice, Nové Hodějovice, and Stará Pohůrka, a part of the village Srubec (7053, GPS 48°57'N, 14°30'E). The dam is terraced. Three biotopes can be found on the dam: young pine-wood, mesic and dry meadows on slopes and mesic and wet meadows on the terraces. The basin itself consists of the water surface, large, partly mowed reed bush and a small birch grove.

Several trips were made to the location in 2009. The material was obtained via hand-collecting. The shells are deposited in the collection of both authors.

Results

More than twenty shells (both adult and juveniles) and several live individuals of *M. cartusiana* were found on the dam. All were situated on meadow slopes and at its base. It is the first record of this species in South Bohemia (MÍKOVCOVÁ, pers. comm.). Besides *M. cartusiana*, the following species were found: *Arianta arbustorum* (Linné, 1758), *Cepaea hortensis* (Müller, 1774), *Cepaea nemoralis* (Linné, 1758), and *Succinella oblonga* Draparnaud, 1801 on dam, *Zonitoides nitidus* (Müller, 1774), *Perpolita hammonis* (Alder, 1830), and *Punctum pygmaeum* (Draparnaud, 1801) in reed bush.

Discussion

The population of *M. cartusiana* near České Budějovice is isolated. Recently, the mapping of the distribution *M. cartusiana* in the Czech Republic is proceeding (<http://www.biolib.cz>; MÍKOVCOVÁ & JUŘIČKOVÁ 2008). The nearest locality, where *M. cartusiana* has been found, is Beroun in central Bohemia (<http://www.biolib.cz>). On the other hand, *M. cartusiana* is relatively abundant in Austria (e.g. FRANK 1986); possibly, the population of *M. cartusiana* near České Budějovice is connected to the Austrian populations rather than the Czech ones.

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